

Separation of barium from associated elements using poly(dibenzo-18-crown-6)

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A simple and elegant separation method for trace level barium has been developed using poly(dibenzo-18-crown-6) from HBr medium. Ba is quantitatively adsorbed 5.5–8.0 M HBr. From the column Ba is quantitatively eluted with 0.1–5.0 M HCl, 0.1–10.0 M acetic acid. It is possible to separate barium from most of the alkali and alkaline earth elements. The method was extended to the analysis of barium in various rock samples.

One area of cation separations field in which almost all present systems have difficulty is that of separations from strong acidic matrices. Polymeric crown ethers provide the means for selective cation separations from strong acidic matrices. Using poly(dibenzo-18-crown-6) we have reported separations of potassium¹, molybdenum² from HBr medium and separations of uranium³, barium⁴, lead⁵, gallium⁶ from HCl medium and thorium⁷ from nitrate medium. Here, the systematic separation study of barium from other elements in HBr medium using poly(DB-18-C-6) and column chromatography is presented. The method has been extended to the separation of barium from a number of elements in binary and multicomponent mixtures and also from a number of real samples.

Results and Discussion

Adsorption of barium as a function of [HBr] on poly(dibenzo-18-crown-6): The concentration of HBr was varied from 0.5 to 8.0 M. After adsorption, barium was eluted with 1.0 M acetic acid. The results reveal that the adsorption of barium starts at 0.5 M (15%) and increases with increase in HBr concentration. The adsorption of barium is 27% at 1.0 M, 52% at 2.0 M, 62% at 3.0 M, 78% at 4.0 M, 98% at 5.0 M and quantitative in 5.5–8.0 M HBr. The subsequent adsorption studies on barium were carried out with 7.0 M HBr.

Elution studies of Ba: After adsorption of barium at 7.0 M HBr, it was eluted from the column with different eluting agents, such as hydrochloric, acetic and perchloric acids in the concentration range 0.1–10.0 M. The elution of barium was found 94% at 0.1 M and quantitative at 0.5–1.0 M, but with increase in HCl concentration the elution of barium decreased and there was no elution of barium at 5.0–10.0 M. Acetic acid was found to be an efficient eluent for the quantitative elution of barium in the concentration range

0.1–10.0 M. With perchloric acid the elution of Ba was 25% at 0.1 M, decreased drastically at 0.5–4.0 M and not eluted at 5.0–10.0 M perchloric acid.

Effect of varying concentration of Ba: The adsorption studies of barium were carried out on PDB18C6 (1.0 g) column with 7.0 M HBr. The concentration of barium was varied from 100 to 1600 μg in a sample solution of 10 ml. After adsorption of barium was eluted with 1.0 M acetic acid. The adsorption of barium was quantitative up to 1200 μg per 10 ml of sample solution. With increase in barium concentration the adsorption decreased. The capacity of PDB18C6 for barium was found to be 0.874 mmol/g of crown polymer.

Separation of Ba from binary mixtures: To an aliquot of solution (100 μg barium) and the foreign ions, HBr was added so that its concentration was 7.0 M in a total volume of 10 ml. The tolerance limit was set as the amount of foreign ions required to cause $\pm 2\%$ error in the recovery of barium. The solution was passed through a PDB18C6 column pre-conditioned with 7.0 M HBr, at a flow rate of 0.5 ml min⁻¹. Then the column was washed with 7.0 M HBr (15 ml). Various foreign ions were not adsorbed and hence passed through the column. The effluent was collected and analyzed. The tolerance (mg, in parenthesis) limits of various foreign ions are as follows: Cr^{III} (35); Li^I, Cs^I, Fe^{III}, Bi^{III}, Ni^{II} (20); Mg^{II}, Sb^{III}, NO₃⁻ (15); Na^I, Be^{II}, Ca^{II}, Sn^{II}, Al^{III}, La^{III}, Th^{IV}, U^{VI}, Mo^{VI}, I⁻, CH₃COO⁻, BO₃³⁻, ascorbate, tartrate (10); citrate (8); NH₄⁺ (7); Rb^I (6); Sr^{II}, Zn^{II}, Pb^{II}, K^I, Ce^{III}, W^{VI}, SCN⁻, ClO₄⁻, Cl⁻ (5); Cu^{II}, Cr₂O₄²⁻ (3); In^{III} (0.8); Tl^{III} (0.5); Ga^{III} (0.2). Most of the alkali and alkaline earth elements were not adsorbed except potassium which was adsorbed quantitatively along with barium at 7.0 M HBr, and rest of the foreign ions showed very high tolerance limit. Amongst d-block, Fe^{III} and Mo^{VI} were quantitatively adsorbed along with barium. The separation of Ba, K, Mo

and from other elements is shown in Table 1. Most of the *p*-block and *d*-block elements were not adsorbed and showed high tolerance limit. The anions of inorganic and organic acids also showed very high tolerance limit.

Table 1. Separation of barium from multicomponent mixture

(a) Adsorption condition, 5 M HBr :					
Sl. no.	Mixture	Taken μg	Found μg	Recovery %	Eluent
1.	Be ^{II}	1000	1000	100	NAPC
	K ^I	100	100	100	8 M HClO ₄
	Ba ^{II}	100	99	99	1 M CH ₃ COOH
2.	Mg ^{II}	1000	1000	100	NAPC
	K ^I	100	99	99	8 M HClO ₄
	Ba ^{II}	100	100	100	1 M CH ₃ COOH
3.	Ca ^{II}	1000	1000	100	NAPC
	K ^I	100	100	100	8 M HClO ₄
	Ba ^{II}	100	98	98	1 M CH ₃ COOH
4.	Sr ^{II}	1000	990	99	NAPC
	K ^I	100	99	99	8 M HClO ₄
	Ba ^{II}	100	100	100	1 M CH ₃ COOH
(b) Adsorption condition, 6 M HBr :					
1.	Be ^{II}	1000	1000	100	NAPC
	K ^I	100	99	99	8 M HClO ₄
	Ba ^{II}	100	98	98	1 M CH ₃ COOH
	Mo ^{VI}	500	495	99	1 M NH ₄ OH
2.	Ca ^{II}	1000	1000	100	NAPC
	K ^I	100	99	99	8 M HClO ₄
	Ba ^{II}	100	100	100	1 M CH ₃ COOH
	Mo ^{VI}	500	490	98	1 M NH ₄ OH
3.	Sr ^{II}	500	500	100	NAPC
	K ^I	100	100	100	8 M HClO ₄
	Ba ^{II}	100	99	99	1 M CH ₃ COOH
	Mo ^{VI}	500	495	99	1 M NH ₄ OH
4.	Rb ^I	1000	990	99	NAPC
	K ^I	100	98	98	8 M HClO ₄
	Ba ^{II}	100	100	100	1 M CH ₃ COOH
	Mo ^{VI}	500	495	99	1 M NH ₄ OH
(c) Adsorption condition, 7 M HBr :					
1.	Be ^{II}	100	100	100	NAPC
	Fe ^{III}	100	99	99	8 M HClO ₄
	Ba ^{II}	100	99	99	1 M CH ₃ COOH
	Mo ^{VI}	500	490	98	1 M NH ₄ OH
2.	Mn ^{II}	100	100	100	NAPC
	Fe ^{III}	100	98	98	8 M HClO ₄
	Ba ^{II}	100	98	98	1 M CH ₃ COOH
	Mo ^{VI}	500	495	99	1 M NH ₄ OH
3.	Ni ^{II}	100	100	100	NAPC
	Fe ^{III}	100	100	100	8 M HClO ₄
	Ba ^{II}	100	100	100	1 M CH ₃ COOH
	Mo ^{VI}	500	490	98	1 M NH ₄ OH
4.	Pb ^{II}	100	99	99	NAPC
	Fe ^{III}	100	100	100	8 M HClO ₄
	Ba ^{II}	100	98	98	1 M CH ₃ COOH
	Mo ^{VI}	500	500	100	1 M NH ₄ OH

Table-1 (contd.)					
5.	La ^{III}	500	500	100	NAPC
	Fe ^{III}	100	100	100	8 M HClO ₄
	Ba ^{II}	100	98	98	1 M CH ₃ COOH
	Mo ^{VI}	500	500	100	1 M NH ₄ OH
6.	Al ^{III}	100	100	100	NAPC
	Fe ^{III}	100	98	98	8 M HClO ₄
	Ba ^{II}	100	100	100	1 M CH ₃ COOH
	Mo ^{VI}	500	500	100	1 M NH ₄ OH
7.	Hg ^{II}	100	100	100	NAPC
	Fe ^{III}	100	100	100	8 M HClO ₄
	Ba ^{II}	100	98	98	1 M CH ₃ COOH
	Mo ^{VI}	500	490	98	1 M NH ₄ OH

Separation of Ba from multicomponent mixtures : By exploiting the adsorption and elution behavior of various metal ions, barium was separated from a number of associated elements in multicomponent mixtures. When a mixture containing Be^{II}, K^I and Ba^{II} was passed through PDB18C6 column at 5.0 M HBr concentration, Be was not adsorbed hence passed through the column whereas other elements were adsorbed. From the column K was first eluted with 8.0 M perchloric acid and under these conditions barium was not eluted hence retained in the column. Barium was then eluted with 1.0 M acetic acid. The separation of barium from other elements in tertiary mixtures was accomplished by following similar methodology.

Separation of barium from other elements in quaternary mixtures was done as follows. When a mixture containing Be^{II}, K^I, Ba^{II} and Mo^{VI} was passed through the PDB18C6 column at 6.0 M HBr, beryllium was not adsorbed whereas other elements were adsorbed. The adsorbed potassium was first eluted with 8.0 M perchloric acid. Under these conditions Ba and Mo were not eluted. Barium was then eluted with 1.0 M acetic acid and finally molybdenum was eluted with 1.0 M ammonium hydroxide.

When a mixture containing Be^{II}, Fe^{III}, Ba^{II} and Mo^{VI} was passed through the PDB18C6 column at 7.0 M HBr, Be was not adsorbed whereas other elements were adsorbed. The adsorbed iron was first eluted with 8.0 M perchloric acid. Under these conditions Ba and Mo were not eluted. Barium was then eluted with 1.0 M acetic acid and finally molybdenum was eluted with 1.0 M ammonium hydroxide. The separation of barium from other elements was accomplished by following similar methodology and the results of separations are shown in Table 1.

Application to analysis of barium in real samples : The proposed method was extended for the determination of barium in number of certified rock samples such as KC-11, KC-12 (King's College, London), USGS-G2 (US Geological Survey), Basaltic-BR (France) and Syenite-SY-2

Note

(Canada). The rock samples were brought into solution as per the reported procedure⁴. The amount of barium found (reported value in parenthesis) in KC-11 rock sample was 485 ppm (491 ppm) and in KC-12 rock sample 1590 ppm (1600 ppm). In USGS-G2 rock sample it was 1845 ppm (1850 ppm), in SY-2 rock sample 445 ppm (460 ppm) and in BR rock sample 1040 ppm (1050 ppm).

Experimental

A Zeiss spectrophotometer, a digital pH meter (Elico LI-120) with glass and calomel electrode, a digital flame photometer (PE1 0.41) and a Pyrex glass column (20 × 0.8 cm, i.d.) with a glass wool plug at the bottom were used.

Poly(dibenzo-18-crown-6) (PDB18C6) (Merck) was used after screening to 100–200 mesh. A slurry PDB18C6 (0.5 g) was made in distilled deionised water and poured into a Pyrex glass chromatographic column. The column was used after preconditioning with hydrobromic acid of known concentration. A stock solution of barium (1 mg ml⁻¹) was prepared by dissolving barium nitrate (AnalaR) in distilled deionised water and standardised gravimetrically⁸. A solution containing 100 µg ml⁻¹ of barium was prepared by appropriate dilution of the standard stock solution.

General procedure : To an aliquot of solution containing 100 µg of barium, HBr was added in the concentration range 0.5–8.0 M in a total volume of 10 ml. The solution was then passed through PDB18C6 column preconditioned

with the same concentration of HBr as that of the sample solution, at a flow rate of 0.5 ml min⁻¹. The column was then washed with the same concentration of HBr. The adsorbed barium was then eluted with different eluting agents at a flow rate of 0.5 ml min⁻¹. 5 ml fractions were collected and barium content was determined spectrophotometrically⁹ with Sulfonazo III at 640 nm. The concentration of barium was calculated from the calibration curve.

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